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Secondary bacterial infection, often caused by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Spn), is one of the most frequent and severe complications of influenza A virus (IAV)-induced pneumonia. Phenotyping of the pulmonary immune cell landscape after IAV infection revealed a substantial depletion of the tissue-resident alveolar macrophage (TR-AM) population at day 7, which was associated with increased susceptibility to Spn outgrowth. To elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying TR-AM depletion, and to define putative targets for treatment, we combined single-cell transcriptomics and cell-specific PCR profiling in an unbiased manner, using in vivo models of IAV infection and IAV/Spn co-infection. The TNF superfamily 14 (TNFSF14) ligand-receptor axis was revealed as the driving force behind post-influenza TR-AM death during the early infection phase, enabling the transition to pneumococcal pneumonia, while intrapulmonary transfer of genetically modified TR-AMs and antibody-mediated neutralization of specific pathway components alleviated disease severity. With a mainly neutrophilic expression and a high abundance in the bronchoalveolar fluid (BALF) of patients with severe virus-induced ARDS, TNFSF14 emerged as a key determinant of virus-driven lung injury. Targeting the TNFSF14-mediated intercellular communication network in the virus-infected lung can, therefore, improve host defense, minimizing the risk of subsequent bacterial pneumonia, and ameliorating disease outcome.

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TNF Superfamily Member 14 Drives Post-Influenza Depletion of Alveolar Macrophages Enabling Secondary Pneumococcal Pneumonia

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Key words: influenza A virus, pneumonia, alveolar macrophages, TNF superfamily, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*

1 **Abstract**

2 Secondary bacterial infection, often caused by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Spn), is
3 one of the most frequent and severe complications of influenza A virus (IAV)-induced
4 pneumonia. Phenotyping of the pulmonary immune cell landscape after IAV infection
5 revealed a substantial depletion of the tissue-resident alveolar macrophage (TR-AM)
6 population at day 7, which was associated with increased susceptibility to Spn
7 outgrowth. To elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying TR-AM depletion, and
8 to define putative targets for treatment, we combined single-cell transcriptomics and
9 cell-specific PCR profiling in an unbiased manner, using in vivo models of IAV infection
10 and IAV/Spn co-infection. The TNF superfamily 14 (TNFSF14) ligand-receptor axis
11 was revealed as the driving force behind post-influenza TR-AM death during the early
12 infection phase, enabling the transition to pneumococcal pneumonia, while
13 intrapulmonary transfer of genetically modified TR-AMs and antibody-mediated
14 neutralization of specific pathway components alleviated disease severity. With a
15 mainly neutrophilic expression and a high abundance in the bronchoalveolar fluid
16 (BALF) of patients with severe virus-induced ARDS, TNFSF14 emerged as a key
17 determinant of virus-driven lung injury. Targeting the TNFSF14-mediated intercellular
18 communication network in the virus-infected lung can, therefore, improve host defense,
19 minimizing the risk of subsequent bacterial pneumonia, and ameliorating disease
20 outcome.

21

22 **Introduction**

23 Bacterial pneumonia, often caused by Spn, is one of the most common complications
24 of primary IAV infection, increasing the risk of death, intensive care unit (ICU)
25 admission, and requirement for mechanical ventilation (1). While strengthening host
26 defense offers a potential alternative to antibiotics amid globally rising resistance,
27 progress is limited by poor understanding of the immune mechanisms behind severe
28 influenza and the transition to post-viral bacterial pneumonia. Among these, virus-
29 induced depletion of the TR-AM pool is considered a key factor in promoting secondary
30 bacterial pneumonia, alongside epithelial damage, influx of pro-inflammatory cells, and
31 impaired mechanical clearance (2, 3). TR-AM numbers remain relatively unchanged
32 during homeostasis, with the main function of the cells being surfactant clearance and
33 containment of minor infections (4). This tolerogenic programming, however, can be
34 overridden by abundant viral presence, leading to a pro-inflammatory phenotypic
35 switch, including extensive cytokine release and phagocytosis of viral particles and
36 apoptotic cells (4, 5). TR-AM loss, often observed after severe infection and
37 notoriously known as the 'TR-AM disappearance reaction' (6, 7), dramatically
38 increases IAV-associated mortality (8, 9), the specific pathomechanisms behind it
39 remain, however, elusive.

40 The TNFSF involves a variety of structurally homologous ligands with multiple
41 functions during development, homeostasis, and tissue response to injury (10).
42 TNFSF14 or LIGHT [homologous to lymphotoxins, exhibits inducible expression and
43 competes with Herpes Simplex Virus (HSV) glycoprotein D for herpes virus entry
44 mediator (HVEM), a receptor expressed by T-lymphocytes] is widely expressed on
45 cells of the hematopoietic compartment (11, 12). In the lung, TNFSF14 has been
46 associated with airway remodeling in asthma, idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, systemic
47 sclerosis models (13, 14), and more recently, with disease severity in covid-19 (15,

48 16). Still, little is known regarding the pathomechanistic role of TNFSF14 in virus-
49 induced pneumonia.

50 TNFSF14 binds to three different receptors; type I transmembrane lymphotoxin beta
51 receptor (LTbR), HVEM, also known as TNF receptor superfamily 14 (TNFRSF14),
52 and decoy receptor 3 (DcR3), which is only found in primates (10). TNFSF14 receptors
53 have a broad distribution on immune, stromal, and parenchymal cells (17), and
54 orchestrate distinct intracellular pathways. The outcome of TNFSF14 crosslinking to
55 its receptors, therefore, heavily relies on disease context and microenvironmental cues
56 (10). Here, we sought to investigate the molecular mechanisms of post-influenza TR-
57 AM loss and its consequences for host defense in a model of IAV and IAV/Spn
58 infection, aiming at identifying any putative targets for immune-based pneumonia
59 treatment options.

60

61 **Results**

62 **Severe IAV infection increases susceptibility to secondary pneumococcal**
63 **infection**

64 To elucidate the pathomechanisms behind TR-AM death after severe IAV infection and
65 its effect on the establishment of secondary bacterial pneumonia, we established a
66 robust co-infection model (Figure 1A). Disease severity after viral, bacterial, or co-
67 infection was shown to vary in a pathogen- and infection dose-dependent manner.
68 Orotracheal (o.t.) infection of C57BL/6 wild-type (wt) mice with 500 foci-forming units
69 (ffu) IAV A/PR/8/34 decreased mouse survival by 50% 14 days after infection, whereas
70 intranasal infection with 2000 colony-forming units (cfu) Spn Serotype 3 (PN36
71 NCTC7978) did not affect survival (Figure 1B) or weight loss (Figure 1C). However,
72 IAV infection seven days prior to pneumococcal infection caused massive leukocyte
73 infiltration (Figure 1, D-G) and a 100% lethal outcome (Figure 1B). Upon use of lower
74 IAV and Spn doses (250ffu/20cfu on day 7 post-IAV infection, pi), average survival was
75 calculated at 37.5% (Figure 1B). Despite the low infection doses, bacterial load in the
76 BALF of previously IAV-infected mice was remarkably high 48h after pneumococcal
77 infection, whereas PBS-pretreated mice completely cleared the infection (Figure 1H),
78 suggesting an IAV-associated impaired immune response against invading Spn. We,
79 therefore, characterized the leukocyte landscape of the IAV-infected lung, as distinct
80 immune cell populations and their interactions can differentially affect post-influenza
81 bacterial clearance (3, 18, 19). Flow cytometry profiling of BALF leukocytes (gating
82 strategy depicted in Supplemental Figure 1A) revealed cell-specific kinetics over the
83 infection course (Figure 1I). Of note, BALF TR-AM numbers, which started significantly
84 declining on day 3 pi, were almost completely depleted between 7-11 days pi (Figure
85 1J). Similar results were shown for lung-tissue leukocytes (gating strategy in
86 Supplemental Figure 1B), which could not be acquired through BAL due to their sessile

87 nature (Supplemental Figure 2A) (20) or extra-alveolar location (Supplemental Figure
88 2, B-M). Upon co-infection, BALF bacterial outgrowth was observed 24h after
89 pneumococcal infection (Figure 1K), coinciding with the period of maximum TR-AM
90 depletion, despite the abundant presence of bone marrow-derived macrophages
91 (BMDM). TR-AMs presented higher Spn phagocytosis capacity (Figure 1L) and no
92 inferiority in killing capacity to the infection-driven pro-inflammatory BMDM (Figure
93 1M), highlighting the importance of TR-AM preservation for maintaining intact host
94 defense. To address this, we sought to identify the molecular underpinnings of post-
95 influenza TR-AM death.

96

97 **Post-influenza TR-AM death involves the activation of caspase-8**

98 Direct viral infection can lead to epithelial cell apoptosis in IAV-induced pneumonia (21,
99 22), posing the question whether this also drives post-IAV TR-AM depletion. Flow
100 cytometry analysis revealed only a small number of IAV-infected TR-AMs (quantified
101 by virus hemagglutinin (HA) expression) with no significant increase over the infection
102 course (Figure 2A). The majority of HA-negative cells had been depleted by day 7 pi
103 (Figure 2A), implying the involvement of a different mechanism with a much higher
104 impact. In accordance with that, when naïve TR-AMs were ex vivo treated with virus-
105 and cell-free BALF from IAV-infected mice (iBALF) from day 7 pi (day of maximum
106 depletion), we observed a significant decrease in TR-AM survival (Figure 2B) and an
107 increase in caspase-3/7 (Figure 2C) and caspase-8 activity (Figure 2D). Transcriptome
108 analysis of flow-sorted HA-negative TR-AMs on days 3 and 7 pi based on a cell-death
109 gene array revealed an upregulation of multiple apoptosis-related genes, such as *Bax*,
110 *Cd40lg*, and *Cflar*, and necrosis-related genes, including *Bmf*, *Commd4*, *Defb1*, and
111 *Parp1* (Figure 2E and Supplemental Material, Cell death arrays wt data). Fold changes
112 of upregulated genes did not differ significantly from baseline, as cell death is mainly

113 regulated on a (post-)translational level (23). Concomitant flow cytometry analysis,
114 however, revealed a remarkable increase in apoptotic TR-AMs over the infection
115 course (Figure 2F, gating strategy in Supplemental Figure 3A). As a result, we raised
116 the question whether apoptosis inhibition would improve TR-AM survival. Following
117 pre-incubation with a non-toxic concentration (Supplemental Figure 3, B-C) of 50 μ M of
118 a specific caspase-3 (Z-DEVD-FMK) or caspase-8 inhibitor (Z-IETD-FMK), naïve TR-
119 AMs were treated with iBALF. Whereas caspase-3 inhibition only showed a negligible
120 protective effect, TR-AM death was completely abrogated in the caspase-8 inhibition
121 group (Figure 2G). When mice were treated with daily subcutaneous (s.c.) injections
122 of the caspase-8 inhibitor (schematic of experimental layout in Figure 2H), an
123 attenuated weight loss was observed up to day 7 pi (Figure 2I). Caspase-8 inhibition
124 fully protected the TR-AM pool on day 3 pi (Figure 2J), without affecting viral titers
125 (Figure 2K), and significantly mitigated TR-AM loss on day 7 pi (Figure 2L). Caspase-
126 8 is a known orchestrator of cell death, typically activated upon the crosslinking of a
127 soluble ligand to a death receptor (24), which, together with the primarily virus-
128 independent TR-AM apoptosis, hinted at a soluble ligand as a driver of TR-AM death.
129

130 **IAV pneumonia sensitizes TR-AMs to TNFSF14 ligation**

131 Death-inducing members of the TNFSF have been associated with promoting alveolar
132 epithelial cell death and driving post-IAV lung injury (18, 25, 26). As such, we
133 hypothesized that a TNFSF member could be involved in post-IAV TR-AM death and
134 analyzed gene expression patterns of receptors and ligands belonging to the TNFSF
135 signaling network in flow-sorted, HA-negative, TR-AMs from mock-infected and
136 infected mice on days 3 and 7 pi. TNFRSF14, a receptor for TNFSF14, showed a
137 significant upregulation at both time points (Figure 3A and Supplemental material, TNF
138 signaling arrays wt data). TNFRSF14 demonstrated a significant increase in mRNA

139 and cell surface protein expression levels over the infection course and after ex vivo
140 TR-AM stimulation with iBALF (Figure 3, B-D). LTbR, the competitor receptor for
141 TNFSF14, presented no changes in transcriptional regulation, yet a distinct increase
142 in protein expression (Figure 3, B-C, and E). On day 3 pi, the majority of TR-AMs
143 stained positive for TNFSF14 receptors (Supplemental Figure 4A). Regarding TNFSF
144 ligand expression, we confirmed previous reports on IAV-induced upregulation of
145 *Tnfsf10* in lung macrophages (25, 26), whereas *Tnfsf15* and *Tnfsf14* were moderately
146 increased (Figure 3F and Supplemental material, TNF signaling arrays wt data).
147 Overall, severe IAV infection was linked to a total TNFSF14 increase in the mouse
148 lung, as shown by IHC (Figure 3G), qPCR (Figure 3H), and ELISA (Figure 3I). In
149 accordance with that, we observed a significant increase in soluble TNFSF14 in the
150 BALF of patients with influenza or COVID-19 acute respiratory distress syndrome
151 (ARDS), compared to control patients who underwent routine bronchoscopy for
152 diagnostic purposes and revealed normal BALF cellularity (Figure 3J). Based on the
153 distinct kinetics of the two TNFSF14 receptors, we aimed at dissecting any differential
154 roles in post-influenza TR-AM fate. Anti-LTbR TR-AM pre-treatment significantly
155 attenuated the increase in caspase-3/7 activity after iBALF treatment, as opposed to
156 the anti-TNFRSF14 and isotype control groups (Figure 3K). Similar results were
157 observed when we treated naïve wt, *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-}, and *Ltbr*^{-/-} TR-AMs with iBALF (Figure
158 3L), indicating a potential protective effect against soluble death-inducing ligands in
159 the absence of LTbR. In accordance with that, IAV-infected *Ltbr*^{-/-} mice demonstrated
160 a less dramatic drop in TR-AM numbers, compared to wt and *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-} mice (Figure
161 3M), as well as an overall attenuated weight loss on days 7 and 8 pi (Figure 3N). The
162 distinct effects of the two receptors on TR-AM survival and the upregulation of the
163 common TNFSF14 ligand in IAV-infected lungs led us to examine TNFSF14 closer.

164

165 **TNFSF14 drives the depletion of the TR-AM pool in IAV-induced pneumonia**

166 To test whether TNFSF14 only induced apoptosis in a subpopulation of TR-AMs,
167 TNFSF14 receptor expression on TR-AM surface was combined with apoptosis
168 staining (annexin V/7-aminoactinomycin, 7-AAD) at different time points after infection.
169 TNFSF14 receptor-expressing cells comprised approximately 80% of apoptotic TR-
170 AMs on day 3 pi (Supplemental Figure 4B). When we compared TR-AMs regarding
171 apoptosis induction based on TNFSF14 receptor expression, TNFSF14 receptor-
172 positive TR-AMs presented significantly higher apoptosis rates on days 3 and 8 pi,
173 compared to LTbR-TNFRSF14⁻ cells (Figure 4A). To test whether TNFSF14 could
174 directly induce TR-AM death, we treated naïve murine (Figure 4B) and human BALF
175 TR-AMs (Figure 4C) with different concentrations of recombinant TNFSF14
176 (rTNFSF14) for 24h. Treatment with 500ng/ml rTNFSF14 led to an average of 25-35%
177 decrease in TR-AM survival compared to the control PBS/BSA group (Figure 4, B-C)
178 and an increase in caspase-3/7 activity, which was even more pronounced when the
179 same setup was performed with day 3 TR-AMs (Figure 4D). Unlike TR-AMs, epithelial
180 cells, which present a basolateral LTbR and a non-preferential, cytoplasmic
181 TNFRSF14 expression pattern (Supplemental Figure 4, D-G), and are also exposed to
182 homotrimeric, active (27), TNFSF14 in the BALF (Supplemental Figure 4, H-I), did not
183 succumb to TNFSF14-induced apoptosis (Supplemental Figure 4C), mirroring the
184 diverse roles of TNFSF14 signaling, based on cell type and receptor availability.
185 O.t. application of rTNFSF14 to IAV-infected mice (schematics in Figure 4E) led to a
186 significant increase in the number of annexin V⁺ TR-AMs (Figure 4F) and further
187 reduced the already diminished BALF and lavaged-lung-tissue TR-AM numbers on day
188 3 pi (Figure 4, G-H), compared to PBS-treated, IAV-infected controls. No differences
189 could be detected in the numbers of other leukocyte populations, based on rTNFSF14
190 treatment (Supplemental Figure 5, A-E). Concomitantly, TR-AM loss was completely

191 abrogated in the BALF and lavaged lung tissue of *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice (Figure 5, A-B). This
192 result could not be reproduced in *Tnfsf10*^{-/-} mice (Supplemental Figure 5F), despite
193 TNFSF10 being one of the pro-apoptotic ligands highly expressed in the BALF after
194 IAV infection (25, 26), suggesting a ligand-specific induction of TR-AM apoptosis.
195 Flow-sorted *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} TR-AMs showed lower induction of apoptosis, necrosis, and
196 autophagy-related genes (Figure 5, C-D, Supplemental Figure 5, G-J, Supplemental
197 material, Cell death arrays *Tnfsf14* ko data) on days 3 and 7 pi, compared to wt mice.
198 Unlike wt iBALF, caspase-3/7 activity was not increased upon TR-AM treatment with
199 *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} iBALF (Figure 5E). No differences could be detected in viral titers on day 3
200 pi (peak of viral replication in this model (28), Supplemental Figure 5K) or in the amount
201 of epithelial (EpcAM+), endothelial (CD31+), and mesenchymal cells (MC,
202 Supplemental Figure 5, L-N). With the exception of neutrophils, which presented higher
203 numbers in *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice on day 3 pi but not at later time points (Supplemental Figure
204 5O), no differences could be shown for other BALF leukocyte populations
205 (Supplemental Figure 5, P-S). This data suggested that TNFSF14-associated cell
206 death was confined to the TR-AM compartment. Alongside, absence of the ligand
207 resulted in decreased weight loss, hinting at a beneficial effect of TNFSF14 blockade
208 (Figure 5F). Aiming at a therapeutic approach, we used a neutralizing anti-TNFSF14
209 antibody (11) and observed higher BALF and lung tissue TR-AM numbers on day 7 pi
210 (Figure 5, G-H), an attenuated weight loss in the anti-TNFSF14 group (Figure 5I), and
211 confirmed lower caspase-3 activity in TR-AMs after ex vivo iBALF treatment (Figure
212 5J), highlighting TNFSF14 as the driver of post-influenza TR-AM death.

213

214 **TNFSF14 is released by neutrophils during the acute IAV infection phase**

215 To identify the cellular source of TNFSF14 during IAV pneumonia, we analyzed
216 expression of the transmembrane form of TNFSF14 on leukocytes (CD45⁺ cells),

217 epithelial cells, MC, and endothelial cells in the lungs of mock- and IAV-infected mice
218 on day 7 pi. TNFSF14 expression was significantly increased in epithelial cells and
219 leukocytes (Figure 6A). This was in accordance with our IHC data, which revealed a
220 prominent signal increase within the leukocyte-infiltrated interstitium and alveolar
221 space on day 7 pi (Figure 6B). Soluble TNFSF14 was detected in the serum of infected
222 mice as early as day 3 pi, further suggesting that blood-derived immune cells
223 contributed to the increase in TNFSF14 levels within the lung (Figure 6C). Single cell
224 (sc)RNA-Seq analysis of pre-gated CD45+ cells from whole lung digests on days 3
225 and 7 pi revealed a total of 14 immune cell clusters on day 3 pi, including TR-AMs,
226 BMDM, interstitial macrophages (IM), B and T cells, conventional dendritic cells
227 (cDCs), plasmacytoid DCs (pDCs), monocyte-derived DCs (moDCs), NK cells, three
228 monocyte clusters with different gene signatures: monocytes 1 (*Ccr2, Ly6a2, F13a1,*
229 *Mgst1, Aldh2*), monocytes 2 (*Tgfb1, Sirpb1c, Otulin1, Plcg2, Zfp710*), and monocytes
230 3 (*Eno3, Cd300e, Agpat4, Rbpms, Slc12a2*), and two neutrophil clusters: neutrophils
231 1 (*Ier5, Ier3, Smox, Gm8995, Ccrl2*) and neutrophils 2 (*Picalm, Jund, Hmgb2,*
232 *Map11c3b, Slc2a3*). Eleven clusters were identified on day 7 pi, including TR-AMs,
233 BMDM, IM, B cells, CD4+, CD8+, proliferating T cells, pDCs, cDCs, NK cells, and
234 neutrophils (Figure 6, D-E). On both time points, neutrophils were revealed as the main
235 leukocyte population expressing *Tnfsf14*, with a minor contribution from NK and T cells.
236 *Ltbr* gene expression was higher than *Tnfsf14* in all monocyte/macrophage
237 populations, including TR-AMs (Figure 6, D-E). qPCR analysis revealed an
238 upregulation of *Tnfsf14* in neutrophils isolated from peripheral blood on day 2 pi,
239 (Figure 6F), recapitulated in BALF neutrophils of patients with IAV ARDS (Figure 6G).
240 Flow cytometry analysis confirmed neutrophils as the main TNFSF14-expressing
241 leukocyte population on day 3 pi, with no ligand expression on bone marrow-derived
242 neutrophils from non-infected mice (Figure 6H). Both soluble and transmembrane

243 TNFSF14 were revealed to contribute to TR-AM apoptosis, as iBALF treatment of day
244 3 TR-AMs led to a significant increase in caspase3-/7 activity, comparable to the
245 increase induced by TR-AM co-culture with day 3 neutrophils, even at the presence of
246 a metalloproteinase inhibitor preventing TNFSF14 shedding (Supplemental Figure 6A)
247 (29). We then tested whether neutrophil depletion via i.p. administration of an anti-
248 Ly6G antibody (30) would improve post-influenza TR-AM survival. Following
249 successful neutrophil depletion (Supplemental Figure 6, B-E), mice demonstrated an
250 attenuated weight loss up to day 7 pi (Supplemental Figure 6F), which was in
251 accordance with previously published data (31, 32). Neutrophil-depleted mice
252 presented lower TNFSF14 levels (Figure 6, I-J), compared to the isotype-treated
253 group, with higher BALF and lung-tissue TR-AM numbers on day 7 pi (Figure 6, K-L).
254 No significant differences in other BALF immune cells could be observed
255 (Supplemental Figure 6, G-K), demonstrating the depletion specificity of the anti-Ly6G
256 antibody.

257

258 **Outcome of post-influenza pneumococcal pneumonia is improved by targeting** 259 **the TNFSF14 ligand-receptor axis**

260 Having established that TR-AM loss was driven by the TNFSF14-LTbR axis in severe
261 IAV infection, we tested whether TR-AM preservation would improve co-infection
262 outcome (Figure 1, A-D). Indeed, *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice showed significantly improved survival
263 and reduced weight loss (Figure 7, A-B), and reduced BALF pneumococcal burden on
264 day 9 pi/48h post-Spn (Figure 7, C-D), whereas no difference could be shown for
265 spleen bacterial burden (Supplemental Figure 7A). Despite a massive neutrophil influx
266 in both groups (Supplemental Figure 7B), *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice maintained TR-AMs (Figure
267 7E). No significant differences could be observed in the phagocytosis capacity and the
268 percentage of phagocytic TR-AMs on day 7 pi, the time point of pneumococcal infection

269 (Supplemental Figure 7, C-D). Based on the lack of difference in overall phagocytic
270 capacity, we concluded that the improved bacterial clearance in *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice was
271 mainly attributed to the higher number of surviving TR-AMs. Treatment with the
272 neutralizing anti-TNFSF14 antibody led to a similar improvement in survival and weight
273 loss (Figure 7, F-G), supporting the hypothesis that post-influenza TR-AM
274 maintenance was key to survive secondary pneumococcal infection. Finally, we
275 performed orthotopic transfer of wt, *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-}, or *Ltbr*^{-/-} TR-AMs in co-infected mice
276 (schematics in Figure 7H). Pneumococcal superinfection proved lethal in mice that
277 received no cells or *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-} TR-AMs, whereas transfer of *Ltbr*^{-/-} TR-AMs rescued
278 75% of mice (Figure 7I). Transfer of wt TR-AMs only slightly increased survival,
279 indicating that transferred wt TR-AMs experienced TNFSF14-dependent apoptosis
280 after transfer on day 3 pi. *Ltbr*^{-/-} TR-AMs additionally showed a superior phagocytosis
281 capacity for Spn compared to wt TR-AMs when infected ex vivo (Figure 7J), which may
282 have additionally contributed to the improved survival observed in the *Ltbr*^{-/-} TR-AM
283 recipient group. Based on these results, we conclude that targeting the TNFSF14
284 signaling axis could revert TR-AM death in the aftermath of severe IAV-induced lung
285 injury and thus prevent the transition to secondary bacterial pneumonia (Figure 7K).
286

287 **Discussion**

288 Lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs) are a leading global cause of death, with IAV
289 infection playing a major role due to a variety of potential complications, most notably
290 secondary bacterial infections, which greatly increase the risk of respiratory failure and
291 ICU admission, and overall mortality (21, 33, 34). With no causative pharmacological
292 treatment for pneumonia-related lung injury, research has focused on understanding
293 the mechanisms behind severe IAV pneumonia and the transition to post-influenza
294 secondary infection. Proposed mechanisms include bacterial dissemination due to
295 IAV-associated epithelial cell death, fibrin deposition, impaired mechanical clearance,
296 microbial dysbiosis, and interferon-driven suppression of phagocyte function (2, 35,
297 36). As the lungs' first line of defense, IAV-induced TR-AM depletion is a critical step
298 in compromising host immunity. Patient and animal studies have demonstrated that
299 severe viral infections drive TR-AM depletion and niche replenishment by BMDM, with
300 the depletion phase aligning with peak susceptibility to bacterial infection (3, 37-39),
301 yet the involved pathways remain poorly understood. Here, we identified TNFSF14 as
302 a driver of TR-AM loss during IAV pneumonia.

303 In the first week post-infection, TR-AM numbers progressively declined, while other
304 leukocytes gradually entered the alveoli in response to viral infection. TR-AM fate after
305 acute infection is dictated by cell death-inducing mechanisms, impaired self-renewal
306 capacity, and loss of pro-survival signals from the injured neighboring epithelium (6,
307 7). The extent of TR-AM depletion and the intensity of the inflammatory response
308 shape the composition and (re)programming of lung-resident cells after infection (40).
309 Our own previous data indicates that partial TR-AM loss enables the recruitment of
310 circulating BMDM, which are essential for post-viral repair through their transitioning
311 into pro-homeostatic phenotypes (41). Co-existence of newly recruited BMDM and
312 surviving original TR-AMs is the outcome of a balanced immune response, which

313 culminates in BMDM-orchestrated tissue repair and return to homeostasis, assisted by
314 the tolerogenic functions of TR-AMs, aimed at restricting epithelial damage (42, 43).
315 Infection severity determines the extent of TR-AM depletion, with a dramatic loss upon
316 severe IAV pneumonia, as demonstrated in our model. Recruitment of pro-
317 inflammatory immune cells and chemokine abundance contribute to viral clearance,
318 but can also escalate to a dysbalanced immune response (44). The highly pro-
319 inflammatory programming of BMDM can aggravate local injury and promote aberrant
320 lung remodeling (18, 28), while dysregulated neutrophil migration and activation
321 positively correlate with disease severity and poor patient outcomes (45, 46). Following
322 TR-AM depletion, early recruitment of professional phagocytes such as BMDM and
323 neutrophils failed to control bacterial spread, leading to dramatic bacterial outgrowth
324 within 24h of Spn infection. This aligns with prior studies demonstrating high
325 susceptibility to secondary pneumococcal infection 5-7 days after IAV infection,
326 coinciding with the TR-AM depletion phase (3). IFN- γ , which is profusely released in
327 the alveoli as part of the antiviral response, heavily impairs TR-AM antibacterial
328 properties, as it downregulates the macrophage receptor with collagenous structure
329 scavenger receptor (MARCO) on TR-AM surface, one of the key elements in TR-AM
330 antibacterial response (47, 48). Defective chemokine production by macrophages, as
331 observed in severe IAV infection and sepsis models, further aggravates disease
332 outcome (49, 50). The near-complete TR-AM loss within a microenvironment of
333 exuberant death-inducing signals in our model highlights an additional important step
334 towards the establishment of lethal post-viral pneumococcal pneumonia. Though a
335 considerable advantage in terms of antibacterial properties has been described for
336 infection-experienced BMDM and newly originating, BMDM-derived, TR-AMs after IAV
337 infection (19), pneumococcal infection in that model was performed weeks after the
338 initial viral hit, as opposed to the window of increased host vulnerability during the acute

339 infection phase described in our study. At this point, TR-AMs showed superior
340 phagocytic capacity and similar killing capacity to BMDM. Thus, preserving TR-AMs
341 early on, may provide critical protection until re-establishment of a fully functional
342 resident macrophage niche, including infection-trained BMDM, has been completed.
343 The remarkable TR-AM loss in C57BL/6 wild-type mice in our study differs from
344 previously published data, where mouse genetic strain determined TR-AM survival,
345 with BALB/c mice exhibiting a drastic TR-AM reduction, as opposed to C57BL/6 mice,
346 which maintained TR-AMs of an altered phenotype (51). In this study by Califano et
347 al., a relatively low dose of IAV PR8 was administered intranasally, whereas we
348 administered a high viral dose orotracheally, aiming at inducing severe pneumonia.
349 Animal strain and administration route for the infection may, therefore, depict a
350 limitation of our study, as results may differ for different in vivo models.
351 Transcriptomic and flow cytometry analyses revealed apoptosis as the primary cause
352 of post-influenza TR-AM death, largely independent of direct viral infection, suggesting
353 the involvement of a death-inducing ligand. While apoptosis promotes early viral
354 spread (22, 52), it also limits infection through elimination of infected cells (53, 54).
355 Leukocyte- and virus-driven alveolar epithelial cell apoptosis, however, compromises
356 the gas-blood barrier and impairs gas exchange (25, 28). Apoptosis inhibition can,
357 therefore, influence infection outcome. To compensate for any effect of caspase
358 inhibition on early virus propagation, we began our treatment on day 2 pi and observed
359 no significant difference in viral titers on day 3 pi, the peak of viral replication in this
360 model (28). Caspase-8 inhibition was chosen based on our in vitro data, which showed
361 a clear advantage over caspase-3 inhibition after TR-AM iBALF treatment. This initially
362 surprising result could be potentially explained through PANoptosis as the joint result
363 of pyroptosis, apoptosis, and necroptosis. This would permit cell death via caspase-3-
364 independent apoptosis or pyroptosis. Caspase-8 is involved in both these pathways

365 (55-58) and is currently the only known programmed cell death (PCD) member that
366 connects all PCD pathways. This can explain the complete abrogation of TR-AM death
367 on day 3 pi, the reduced weight loss, and the improved TR-AM survival upon caspase-
368 8 inhibition. Nevertheless, the PANoptosis concept suggests that a single PCD
369 component cannot individually rescue cells once PANoptosis has been initiated, which
370 might explain why TR-AM loss was not completely prevented on day 7 pi, when death-
371 inducing signals are highly abundant (59-61).

372 Stochastic interrogation of TNFSF members revealed significant upregulation of
373 TNFSF14 in infected mouse lungs, with high soluble TNFSF14 levels also found in
374 BALF from patients with severe virus-induced ARDS. Previous studies on severe viral
375 pneumonia and sepsis positively linked elevated BALF/serum TNFSF14 levels to
376 disease severity (15, 16, 62, 63). Depending on cell type, pathogen interaction, and
377 receptor availability, TNFSF14 can influence cell survival, profile (re)programming,
378 immune response establishment, and infection memory (10, 64). TNFSF14 has been
379 previously described as a determinant of macrophage survival, phenotype, and
380 antibacterial properties (65-67), however, extensive studies regarding post-influenza
381 TR-AM death are lacking. In our study, TNFSF14 deletion or blockade preserved TR-
382 AMs and improved survival and weight loss during co-infection. These benefits were
383 not solely due to reduced bacterial burden but likely stemmed from enhanced tissue
384 repair and accelerated return to homeostasis due to improved TR-AM survival.
385 Previous work from our lab has highlighted TR-AMs as drivers of epithelial repair (41)
386 and mitigators of lung inflammation, even at the cost of bacterial clearance (43).
387 Further experiments would be required to fully address the role of TNFSF14 on
388 pathogen resistance and tolerance in the context of co-infection beyond the lung-
389 confined effect on TR-AM survival.

390 Post-influenza TNFSF14-induced TR-AM death was cell-specific, with no significant
391 differences in other leukocytes (except neutrophils on day 3 pi) or in endothelial,
392 mesenchymal, or epithelial cells between wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice. TNFSF14 treatment
393 did not worsen virus-induced death in alveolar epithelial cells, suggesting TNFSF14 is
394 not a strong driver of post-influenza distal epithelial cell apoptosis. We identified
395 neutrophils as the main leukocyte source of TNFSF14, which is in accordance with
396 previously published data (68, 69). TNFSF14 has been shown to play an instrumental
397 role in NK and T cell activation and expansion (11, 17, 70) and DC maturation (71) and
398 may thus serve as an intermediate between the acute and adaptive immune response.
399 Aberrant release due to dysregulated neutrophil activation could offer an alternative
400 explanation for the abundant TNFSF14 presence upon severe infection. This is in
401 accordance with literature, as high circulating or organ-specific TNFSF14 levels have
402 been positively correlated with highly inflammatory states (13, 15, 72-74) and blocking
403 of the ligand was shown to limit inflammation and attenuate organ injury (75).

404 TNFRSF14 and LTbR, the two competitor TNFSF14 receptors, followed distinct
405 kinetics in terms of transcriptional regulation and protein expression in TR-AMs during
406 the infection course. Attenuated TR-AM loss after IAV infection of *Ltbr*^{-/-} mice,
407 compared to *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-} mice, and improved survival after intrapulmonary transfer of
408 *Ltbr*^{-/-} TR-AMs to co-infected wt mice, demonstrated a stronger impact on TR-AM death
409 for LTbR. Given the more prominent TR-AM preservation in *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice compared
410 to *Ltbr*^{-/-} mice, we hypothesize that cell death could also be initiated through ligation of
411 TNFSF14 to TNFRSF14, potentially through activation of a co-receptor, as TNFRSF14
412 lacks a pro-death domain (10, 76). It should be noted, however, that engagement of
413 LTbR by TNFSF14 on macrophages is not merely confined to apoptosis induction.
414 Transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) can be secreted upon crosslinking (77),
415 which has been shown to drive an immunoparalysis state in the aftermath of infection,

416 further enhancing secondary infection susceptibility (78). LTbR-TNFSF14 interaction
417 on the endothelium alters microvasculature structure, which can in turn favor the
418 recruitment of immune cells (79). The intricate nature of TNFSF14-TNFRSF14/LTbR
419 interactions thus points at a multitude of potential roles for the signaling axis in the
420 context of influenza, besides TR-AM depletion. Nevertheless, with clinical trials in the
421 context of virus-induced pneumonia and systemic inflammation already revealing
422 beneficial safety profiles (63, 80, 81), therapeutic interventions disrupting TNFSF14-
423 initiated intercellular pathways to preserve TR-AM function appear as promising
424 approaches for improving host defense in the context of IAV pneumonia.

425

426 **Methods**

427 *Sex as a biological variable.* Sex was not considered as a biological variable for patient
428 samples. Both male and female mice were used for all studies.

429 *Mice.* Wt C57BL/6 mice were purchased from Charles River Laboratories. *Tnfsf14*^{-/-}
430 (82), *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-} (83), and *Ltbr*^{-/-} (84) mice were a gift from Prof. Klaus Pfeffer (Heinrich
431 Heine University Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf, Germany). *Tnfsf10*^{-/-} (85) mice were obtained
432 from AMGen. All mice were bred under specific-pathogen-free conditions (SPF) and
433 infected at 10-12 weeks of age.

434 *In vivo infection.* For in vivo IAV infection experiments, mice were orotracheally
435 inoculated with 250-1000ffu of A/Puerto Rico/8/1934 (PR8, H1N1) influenza virus.
436 Control groups were inoculated with sterile PBS^{-/-}. For co-infection experiments, mice
437 were i.n. infected with 20cfu Spn [serotype 3, strain PN36 (NCTC 7978), provided by
438 the group of M. Witzernath, Department of Infectious Diseases and Pulmonary
439 Medicine, Charité, University Medicine Berlin, Berlin, Germany] 7 days after IAV
440 infection.

441 *In vivo treatment.* For apoptosis inhibition, wt mice were infected with 500ffu (day 7
442 experiments) or 1000ffu IAV (day 3 experiments) and treated with s.c. injections of
443 10mg/kg of a specific caspase-8 inhibitor (Z-IETD-FMK, R&D Systems), or a DMSO
444 control. For day 3 experiments, treatment involved a single injection on day 2 pi,
445 whereas daily injections were applied days 2-6 pi for analysis on day 7 pi. Neutrophil
446 depletion was performed through the i.p. application of 200µg anti-1A8 antibody
447 (*InVivoPlus* rat anti-mouse Ly6G, cat. BP0075-1, BioXCell) or an anti-2A3 isotype
448 control (*InVivoPlus*TM rat IgG2a isotype control, anti-trinitrophenol, cat. BP0089,
449 BioXCell) diluted in sterile PBS in mice infected with 500ffu IAV on days -1, 1, 3, and
450 5 pi. TNFSF14 neutralization was achieved with a mouse anti-mouse LIGHT blocking
451 antibody (clone 3D11, IgG2b, k, isotype control mouse IgG2b, clone 27-35,

452 BioLegend), kindly provided by Prof. José Ignacio Rodríguez Barbosa and Prof. Maria-
453 Luisa del Rio (INBIOMIC, University of León, León, Spain). A single i.p. injection of
454 500µg of antibody or isotype control was performed two days after IAV infection with
455 500ffu. For in vivo treatment with rTNFSF14, 10µg of carrier-free mouse rTNFSF14
456 (cat. 1794-LT, R&D Systems) diluted in 0.03mL PBS^{-/-} were orotracheally administered
457 to IAV-infected mice on days 1 and 2 pi for analysis on day 3 pi.

458 *Adoptive TR-AM transfer.* Murine TR-AM were obtained from the BALF of naïve wt,
459 *Tnfrsf14^{-/-}*, and *Ltbr^{-/-}* mice, as previously described (25). Adoptive transfer of 400,000
460 TR-AM per mouse was performed on day 3 after infection of wt mice with 250ffu IAV,
461 with an engraftment efficiency of 14-20% calculated 24h later, at a time point where
462 over 70% of the original TR-AM pool was still detectable in the BALF of infected mice
463 (data not shown). Secondary pneumococcal infection was performed four days later.

464 *TR-AM isolation and cell culture for ex vivo treatment.* Following BALF extraction from
465 naïve mice, cells were resuspended in full TR-AM medium (RPMI-1640/2% fetal
466 bovine serum (FBS)/2.5% HEPES/1% L-glutamine/1% penicillin/streptomycin). TR-
467 AMs were seeded at a density of 10-50,000 cells/well on a 96-well plate.

468 *Colorimetric viability assay for ex vivo treated TR-AMs.* Primary TR-AMs isolated from
469 the BALF of naïve wt mice and BALF TR-AMs from control patients who underwent
470 routine bronchoscopy for diagnostic purposes and revealed normal BALF cellularity
471 were treated with 0.1mL TR-AM medium containing 10% iBALF or rTNFSF14 for 24h.
472 For caspase inhibition experiments, cells were pre-incubated in 50µM of a specific
473 caspase-3 (Z-DEVD-FMK, cat. FMK004, R&D Systems) or caspase-8 inhibitor (Z-
474 IETD-FMK, cat. FMK007, R&D Systems) for 3h prior to BALF treatment. Viability was
475 assessed via colorimetric assay (Cell Counting Kit-8, cat. 96992, Sigma Aldrich), as
476 per the manufacturer's instructions, and was considered proportional to the measured
477 light absorbance. Absorbance was measured in an iMark microplate reader (Bio-Rad).

478 *Caspase-3/7 and caspase-8 activity.* Wt, *Tnfrsf14^{-/-}*, and *Ltbr^{-/-}* BALF TR-AMs were
479 treated with 0.1mL TR-AM medium containing 10% day 0 or day 7 iBALF from wt or
480 *Tnfsf14^{-/-}* mice for 24h. Lyophilized Caspase-Glo[®] 3/7 or Caspase-Glo[®] 8 substrate
481 (Promega) was resuspended in 10mL luciferase-containing Caspase-Glo[®] buffer
482 (Promega) and added á 0.1mL/well to the cells. After 1h incubation at RT, cells were
483 transferred to a black 96-well plate for luminescence detection using a 520/25 filter in
484 an FLx800 fluorescence reader (BioTek Instruments). For ligand blocking experiments,
485 iBALF had been previously incubated with 1µg/mL of the mouse anti-mouse TNFSF14
486 antibody or an isotype control for 1h at 4°C prior to iBALF treatment. For TNFSF14
487 receptor blocking experiments, TR-AMs were pretreated with 1µg/mL for 1h at 37°C,
488 CO₂, prior to iBALF treatment, to achieve receptor saturation. Antibodies included
489 Armenian hamster anti-mouse anti-TNFRSF14 (CD270 (HVEM) monoclonal antibody,
490 LH1, functional grade, cat. 16-5962-85, eBioscience™), Armenian hamster anti-mouse
491 isotype control (cat. 16-4888-85, eBioscience™), rat anti-mouse anti-LTbR (clone 4H8-
492 WH2, developed by the laboratory of Dr. Carl F. Ware, marketed by AdipoGen Life
493 Sciences, and kindly provided by Prof. José Ignacio Rodríguez Barbosa and Prof.
494 Maria-Luisa del Rio, University of León, Spain), and rat anti-mouse IgG2a isotype
495 control (cat. AG-35B-0002-C050, AdipoGen). To dissect the roles of soluble and
496 transmembrane TNFSF14 on TR-AM apoptosis, flow-sorted day 3 TR-AMs were either
497 treated with iBALF or co-cultured with neutrophils at a 1:5 ratio for 24h. Marimastat
498 (cat. M2699, Sigma-Aldrich) was added at a concentration of 10µM to prevent
499 TNFSF14 shedding.

500 *Spn load after in vivo infection.* Two days after IAV infection and 6-72h after Spn
501 infection, BALF, lungs, and spleens from co-infected mice were harvested and
502 homogenized. A series of inoculum dilutions in NaCl was prepared for each sample in
503 1:10 dilution steps. For each dilution step, 4 x 0.01mL inoculum were pipetted on a

504 blood agar plate and stored at 37°C overnight. Bacterial load was calculated by
505 counting the average number of separately grown colonies, multiplied by $10^{\text{number of}}$
506 $\text{dilution step} \times 100$ (= number of colonies in 1mL).

507 *Ex vivo phagocytosis and killing assay.* *Wt* and *Ltbr*^{-/-} naïve BALF TR-AMs were
508 isolated as previously described. Cells were seeded á 100,000 cells/well on a 96-well
509 round-bottom plate and ex vivo infected with Spn at an multiplicity of infection (MOI)
510 1000 for 10min (37°C). Cells were vigorously washed 5 times in ice-cold PBS to
511 remove any extracellular bacteria and lysed in water. An inoculum dilution series of cell
512 lysates was pipetted on blood agar plates as described above. Total colony count on
513 the following day depicted phagocytosed bacteria. For flow cytometry-based
514 comparison of day 8 TR-AMs and BMDM Spn uptake and killing, 100,000 cells of whole
515 BALF cell samples were ex vivo infected with Spn at an MOI 100 for 10min (t₀). Cells
516 were washed three times with ice-cold PBS and were either fixed and permeabilized
517 using the eBioscience™ Foxp3/Transcription Factor Staining Buffer Set (cat. 00-5523-
518 00, Invitrogen), as per the manufacturer's instructions, or returned to the incubator for
519 an additional 30min (t₁) in sterile medium, after which the same procedure was
520 performed. Staining was performed in two steps, starting with an anti-Spn antibody
521 (rabbit, cat. PA17259, Invitrogen) or a rabbit IgG isotype control (cat. ab172730,
522 abcam) at a concentration of 40µg/mL for 1h at RT, followed by leukocyte surface
523 staining containing a secondary donkey anti-rabbit IgG (H+L) Alexa Fluor™ 555
524 antibody (cat. A-31572, Invitrogen). Non-infected samples were used as
525 autofluorescence controls. Phagocytosis capacity was reflected in the percentage of
526 Spn+ cells at (t₀), killing capacity at (t₁) was determined for each macrophage
527 population as follows: percent killing = $100 - [(\% \text{Spn}^+ \text{ cells at } t_1 / \% \text{Spn}^+ \text{ cells at } t_0) \times$
528 $100]$.

529 *RT² Profiler PCR Arrays.* RT² profiler PCR arrays (Qiagen) were used for pathway or
530 group gene expression analysis of flow-sorted TR-AMs. RNA isolation, genomic DNA
531 elimination, reverse transcription, cDNA synthesis, and qPCR were performed
532 according to the manufacturer's instructions. In samples with low RNA amount (<1µg),
533 a pre-amplification of cDNA targets preceded qPCR by addition of a PCR master mix
534 (RT² PreAMP PCR Mastermix, Qiagen) and a species- and pathway-specific primer
535 mix (PBM-063Z-RT² PreAMP cDNA Synthesis Primer Mix for Mouse TNF Ligands and
536 Receptors, PBM-212Z - RT² PreAMP cDNA Synthesis Primer Mix for Mouse Cell
537 Death PathwayFinder™, cat.330241, Qiagen) to the cDNA samples. PCR components
538 were added to the 96-well plate format provided by the company (PAMM-063ZC-24-
539 RT² Profiler™ PCR Array Mouse TNF Signaling Pathway, PAMM-212ZC-12-RT²
540 Profiler™ PCR Array Mouse Cell Death PathwayFinder, cat. 330231, Qiagen). Real-
541 time PCR was performed in the StepOnePlus™ Real-Time PCR System and in the
542 QuantStudio™ 3 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems™). Data analysis was
543 performed with the company's web-based data analysis software (GeneGlobe Data
544 Analysis Center, Qiagen). A detailed description of the data statistical interpretation
545 can be found in the 'Supplemental methods' document.

546 *Single-cell RNA sequencing.* To identify the main leukocyte TNFSF14 source, 500,000
547 live leukocytes (gated as Sytox- CD45+) from the homogenized single-cell lung
548 suspensions of IAV-infected mice on day 3 and 7pi were sorted into 0.35µL 0.04%
549 BSA/PBS^{-/-}. Following viability control, 10,000 cells were loaded onto Chromium Chip
550 B (10X Genomics). Gel beads in emulsion (GEM) generation, cDNA synthesis and
551 amplification, and library preparation were performed with the Chromium Single Cell 3'
552 Reagent Kit v3.1 (10X Genomics), as per the manufacturer's protocol. Indexed libraries
553 were sequenced on an Illumina NextSeq2000. Prior to analysis, reads were aligned
554 against the mouse genome (GRCm38.p6) and quantified using StarSolo

555 (<https://github.com/alexdobin/STAR>). Analysis was conducted with the Scanpy
556 software (<https://github.com/theislab/scanpy>). After quality filtering, raw cell counts
557 were normalized to the median count over all cells and transformed into log space for
558 variance stabilization. Principal component analysis (PCA) identified 14 and 11
559 components on days 3 and 7 pi, respectively. Uniform Manifold Approximation and
560 Projection (UMAP) embedding was created to identify cell type clusters through Leiden
561 clustering. Doublet analysis was conducted on day 7 using Scrublet
562 (<https://github.com/swolock/scrublet>), leading to the removal of a doublet cluster (118
563 cells).

564 *Statistics.* Data are shown in scatterplots as single data points. Means \pm SEM per group
565 are indicated by bars and error bars. Statistical significance between two groups was
566 calculated using 2-tailed Student's t-test. For comparison between more than two groups,
567 significance was determined by 1-way ANOVA, 2-way ANOVA with Tukey's posthoc test,
568 or by Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's post hoc comparison test. Survival curves
569 were compared by log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test. $P < 0.05$ was considered as significant. $*P <$
570 0.05 ; $**P < 0.01$; $***P < 0.005$. Graphs were prepared using GraphPad Prism (GraphPad
571 Software version 10.2.3).

572 *Study approval.* Animal experiments were approved by the regional authorities of the
573 State of Hesse (Regierungspraesidium Giessen, Germany) and by the Institutional
574 Ethics Committee at the IBioBA Institute (Buenos Aires, Argentina). Use of human
575 BALF samples was approved by the University of Giessen Ethics Committee, samples
576 were provided by the biobank of the German Center for Lung Research (DZL). Written
577 informed consent was received prior to sample use.

578 *Data availability.* Data supporting the findings of this study are available within the
579 article and its supplemental material. Values for all data points in graphs are reported
580 in the Supporting Data Values file. ScRNA-Seq data can be accessed under the GEO

583 **Author contributions**

584 CM, CP, MRF, KF, KK, CYW, JB, ME designed and performed experiments,
585 evaluated, and interpreted data. CM wrote the manuscript. AIVA and SH designed,
586 performed, and interpreted scRNA-Seq experiments. IA performed imaging analysis.
587 HS, SG, ML performed sequencing and bioinformatics analyses. JH and ADG
588 performed immunohistochemistry analysis. KP provided genetically modified mice.
589 MLDR and JIRB provided the neutralizing anti-TNFSF14 and anti-LTbR antibodies. IV
590 performed bronchoscopy for the acquisition of human BALF samples. CP, SG, ML,
591 ADG, IV, UM, and SH revised the manuscript. SH conceived the scientific question,
592 designed experiments, interpreted data, and financed the study.

593

594

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 823 **Figure 1. IAV infection increases susceptibility to secondary pneumococcal**
 824 **infection. (A)** Schematic representation of the co-infection model, with pneumococcal
 825 **infection taking place 7 days after IAV infection. (B-C)** Survival (B) and weight loss (C)

826 after IAV/Spn co-infection of wt mice (n=6-8, data pooled from five independent
827 experiments). **(D-G)** Representative histological images of mock-infected **(D)**, Spn-
828 infected **(E)**, IAV-infected **(F)**, or mice infected with IAV 7 days prior to Spn infection
829 **(G)**, lungs harvested ten days after IAV infection. Scale bar set at 100µm, data pooled
830 from two independent experiments. **(H)** Bacterial load in the BALF of IAV- or mock-
831 infected mice nine days after IAV infection and 48h after Spn infection (mean ± SEM,
832 n=6-9, data representative of three independent experiments). **(I)** Leukocyte
833 populations including neutrophils (n=7-9), BMDM (n=8-9), NK cells (n=7-9), T cells
834 (n=3-9), NK1.1⁺ NKT cells (n=3-9), and B cells (n=5-9), in the BALF of IAV-infected
835 mice 0-14 days pi (mean ± SEM, data pooled from sixteen independent experiments).
836 **(J)** TR-AM population during the IAV infection course (means ± SEM, n=3-10, data
837 pooled from six independent experiments). **(K)** BALF bacterial load 6-72h after
838 pneumococcal superinfection performed seven days post-IAV infection (mean ± SEM,
839 n=3-9 per time point, data pooled from three independent experiments). **(L-M)** Spn
840 phagocytosis capacity **(L)** depicted as %Spn⁺ cells 10min (t₀) after infection and killing
841 capacity **(M)**, % killing at t₁ over t₀) for day 8 TR-AMs and BMDM, n=5, data
842 representative of three independent experiments. Significance was determined by log-
843 rank (Mantel-Cox) test, unpaired 2-tailed t-test, and by 1-way ANOVA with Tukey's
844 posthoc test; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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846 **Figure 2. Caspase-8 is involved in virus-independent post-influenza TR-AM**
 847 **death.** (A) Quantification of viral HA-negative and HA-positive TR-AM
 848 infection, mean \pm SEM is depicted, n=3-7, data pooled from three independent
 849 experiments. (B) TR-AM survival following 24h treatment with iBALF. Graphs

850 represent means \pm SEM, n=9 per group, data pooled from three independent
851 experiments. **(C-D)** Caspase-3/7 **(C)** and caspase-8 activity **(D)** after iBALF TR-AM
852 treatment. Graphs represent means \pm SEM, n=7-8, data pooled from three
853 independent experiments, respectively. **(E)** Heat map depicting average fold changes
854 of cell death-related genes in flow-sorted, HA-negative, mock, day 3, and day 7 pi
855 BALF TR-AMs, n=3-7 per time point, data pooled from four independent experiments.
856 **(F)** Percentage of apoptotic TR-AMs on days 0, 3, and 7 pi (means \pm SEM, n=7-12,
857 data pooled from four independent experiments). **(G)** Colorimetric viability assay
858 following naïve TR-AM treatment with iBALF after 3h pre-treatment with 50 μ M of a
859 specific caspase inhibitor (means \pm SEM, n=6). Data pooled from two independent
860 experiments. **(H)** Experimental layout for caspase-8 inhibition in vivo experiments. **(I)**
861 Weight loss after IAV infection and caspase-8 inhibition, n=8-11, data pooled from six
862 independent experiments. **(J)** BALF TR-AMs on day 3 pi after in vivo caspase-8
863 inhibition (means \pm SEM, n=11-13, data pooled from four independent experiments).
864 **(K)**. BALF viral titers on day 3 pi after in vivo caspase-8 inhibition (means \pm SEM, n=3-
865 6, data pooled from two independent experiments). **(L)** BALF TR-AMs on day 7 pi after
866 in vivo caspase-8 inhibition (means \pm SEM, n=7-10, data pooled from seven
867 independent experiments. Significance was determined by 2-tailed t-test of the Areas
868 Under Curve (AUC) for the compared groups in **(I)**, 1-way, or 2 -way ANOVA with
869 Tukey's posthoc test; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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 872 **Figure 3. IAV infection leads to an increased expression of the TNFSF14 ligand-**
 873 **receptor axis. (A)** Fold change of TNFSF receptor genes in mock, day 3, and day 7
 874 TR-AMs (n=5-6, data pooled from three experiments). **(B)** TR-AM *Tnfrsf14* and *Ltbr*
 875 gene expression over IAV infection course, n=3-6, data pooled from two experiments.
 876 **(C)** TR-AM *Tnfrsf14* and *Ltbr* gene expression after ex vivo iBALF treatment (n=5, data
 877 representative of three experiments). **(D-E)** TR-AM TNFRSF14 **(D)** and LTbR **(E)**
 878 expression (n=7-11, data pooled from six experiments). **(F)** Fold change of TNFSF
 879 ligand genes in mock, day 3, and day 7 TR-AMs (n=5-6, data pooled from three
 880 independent experiments). **(G)** IHC analysis for TNFSF14 expression after mock
 881 (PBS) or IAV infection. Scale bar set at 25 μ m (n=6-8, data pooled from two
 882 experiments). **(H)** *Tnfrsf14* gene expression in the lungs of IAV-infected animals (n=7-
 883 8, data pooled from three experiments). **(I)** BALF TNFSF14 measured by ELISA (n=4-

884 15, data pooled from seven experiments). **(J)** Soluble TNFSF14 in the BALF of patients
885 with severe viral pneumonia (n=8-17 per group). Data pooled from three experiments.
886 **(K)** Caspase-3/7 activity after iBALF treatment of naïve wt TR-AM, following anti-LTbR
887 or anti-TNFSF14 blocking (n=15-28, data pooled from six experiments). **(L)** Caspase-
888 3/7 activity after iBALF treatment of naïve wt, *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-}, and *Ltbr*^{-/-} TR-AM (n=6-9, data
889 pooled from four experiments). **(M)** TR-AM numbers of wt, *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-} and *Ltbr*^{-/-} mice
890 on day 0 and 7 pi (n=5-13, data pooled from twelve experiments, wt controls including
891 values depicted in 1J). **(N)** Body weight of wt, *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-}, and *Ltbr*^{-/-} mice over the IAV
892 infection course (n=5 per group, data pooled from three experiments). Graphs
893 represent means ± SEM, significance determined by unpaired 2-tailed t-test, 1-way, 2-
894 way ANOVA with Tukey's posthoc test, and Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's
895 post hoc comparison test; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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898 **Figure 4. TNFSF14 treatment aggravates post-influenza TR-AM loss.** (A)
899 Percentage of apoptotic cells within LTbR⁻ TNFRSF14⁻ and LTbR⁺ and/or TNFRSF14⁺
900 TR-AM subgroups on days 3 and 8 pi. Graphs represent means ± SEM, n=8-10 per
901 group, data pooled from two independent experiments. (B-C) Cell survival proportional
902 to light absorbance after 24h treatment of murine (B) and human (C) TR-AMs with
903 different doses of rTNFSF14 and normalized to control samples. Graph represents
904 means ± SEM, n=5-7. Data in (B) and (C) pooled from seven and four independent
905 experiments, respectively. (D) Caspase-3/7 activity after 24h TR-AM treatment with
906 500ng/ml rTNFSF14 (means ± SEM, n=6-7, data pooled from six independent
907 experiments). (E) Schematics of rTNFSF14 application to IAV-infected mice days 1
908 and 2 pi with analysis performed on day 3 pi. (F) Percentage of live (annexin V⁻ 7-AAD⁻)
909 and apoptotic (annexin V⁺ 7-AAD⁻) TR-AMs (n=3) on day 3 pi after rTNFSF14
910 treatment, data representative of three different experiments. (G-H) Total BALF (n=6-
911 11, G) and lung-tissue TR-AMs (n=7-10, H) on day 3 pi after rTNFSF14 treatment,
912 compared to mock infection. Graphs represent means ± SEM and data is pooled from
913 seven independent experiments. Significance was determined by 1-way or 2-way
914 ANOVA with Tukey's posthoc test; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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Figure 5. Post-influenza TR-AM loss can be prevented through directed targeting of the TNFSF14 ligand. (A-B) BALF TR-AMs (A) and sessile lung TR-AMs (B) in wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice after IAV infection (means ± SEM, n=8-12, data pooled from seventeen different experiments, wt controls in (B) including values depicted in Supplemental Figure 2A). (C-D) Heat maps depicting fold change of apoptosis-related

921 genes on day 3 pi (**C**) and day 7 pi (**D**) over mock-infected wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} TR-AMs,
922 n=3-5, data pooled from five different experiments. Wt data extracted from the data set
923 presented in Figure 2E. (**E**) Caspase-3/7 activity after TR-AM treatment with wt and
924 *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} iBALF. Graph represents means ± SEM, n=4 per condition, data
925 representative of three independent experiments. (**F**) Body weight of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-}
926 mice over the IAV infection course. Graph represents means ± SEM of weight at each
927 time point, n=12-13, data pooled from six independent experiments, wt controls
928 including data presented in Figure 3M). (**G-H**) BALF (**G**) and lung tissue (**H**) TR-AMs
929 on day 7 pi after anti-TNFSF14 treatment on day 2 pi. Graph represents means ± SEM,
930 n=9-13, data pooled from four independent experiments. (**I**) Body weight of anti-
931 TNFSF14 and isotype-treated wt mice after IAV infection. Graph represents means ±
932 SEM of weight at each time point, n=10-11, data pooled from four independent
933 experiments. (**J**) Caspase-3/7 activity after 24h iBALF treatment of anti-TNFSF14 pre-
934 treated naïve TR-AMs. Data pooled from six independent experiments (means ± SEM,
935 n=16). Significance was determined by unpaired 2-tailed t-test, 1-way, or 2-way
936 ANOVA with Tukey's posthoc test; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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Figure 6. Neutrophils are the main cellular source of TNFSF14 during IAV infection. (A) TNFSF14 expression on leukocytes, epithelial, endothelial cells, and MC in the lungs of non-infected and day 7 mice, n=4-5, data pooled from two independent experiments. (B) TNFSF14 expression in different lung regions of mock-

943 and IAV-infected wt mice on day 7 pi (n=3-4, data representative of two independent
944 experiments). Scale bar set at 25µm. **(C)** Serum TNFSF14 on days 0, 3, and 7 pi (n=3-
945 5, data pooled from three independent experiments). **(D-E)** Leukocyte scRNA-Seq
946 analysis on day 3 **(D)** and day 7 pi **(E)**, n=4, data from two independent experiments.
947 Monocyte and neutrophil clusters on day 3 pi were characterized according to the gene
948 signature of the top 5 uniquely expressed genes per cluster. Dot plots depict *Tnfsf14*,
949 *Ltbr*, and *Tnfrsf14* expression. **(F)** qPCR analysis for *Tnfsf14* expression in blood and
950 BALF neutrophils (n=4, data pooled from two independent experiments). **(G)** qPCR
951 analysis for *TNFSF14* expression in BALF neutrophils from patients with severe IAV-
952 induced ARDS compared to non-IAV controls (n=3-4). **(H)** TNFSF14 expression on
953 BALF leukocytes on day 3 pi and bone marrow-derived (BM) neutrophils from non-
954 infected mice, n=3-10, data pooled from two independent experiments. **(I-J)** qPCR
955 analysis in lung tissue, n=7-9 **(I)**, and BALF ELISA, n=9-13 **(J)**, for TNFSF14
956 expression on day 7 pi after neutrophil depletion. Data pooled from four and five
957 independent experiments, respectively. **(K-L)** BALF **(K)** and lung **(L)** TR-AMs on day
958 7 pi after neutrophil depletion (n=8, data pooled from four and five independent
959 experiments, respectively). Graphs represent means ± SEM. Significance was
960 determined by unpaired 2-tailed t-test, 1-way, or 2-way ANOVA; *p<0.05, **p<0.01,
961 ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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Figure 7. Severity of post-influenza pneumococcal pneumonia is attenuated in the absence of TNFSF14. (A-B) Survival (A) and weight loss (B) after IAV/Spn co-infection of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice (means ± SEM, n=17-18, data pooled from five different experiments). (C-D) Bacterial burden in the BALF (C) and in the lungs (D) of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice 9 days after IAV infection and 48h after Spn infection (means ±

969 SEM, n=10, data pooled from eight independent experiments). **(E)** Total BALF TR-AM
970 numbers of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice 9 days after IAV/ 48h after Spn infection (means ±
971 SEM, n=7-8, data pooled from five different experiments). **(F-G)** Survival **(F)** and weight
972 loss **(G)** following IAV/Spn co-infection and TNFSF14 blocking on day 2 pi (means ±
973 SEM, n=12-16, data pooled from five independent experiments). **(H)** Schematics of
974 experimental layout for IAV/Spn co-infection with adoptive transfer (a.t.) of naïve wt,
975 *Tnfrsf14*^{-/-}, or *Ltbr*^{-/-} TR-AMs on day 3 pi. **(I)** Survival of wt mice upon IAV/Spn co-
976 infection and TR-AM a.t. (means ± SEM, n=4-12, data pooled from five independent
977 experiments). **(J)** Bacterial load in lysed wt and *Ltbr*^{-/-} naïve TR-AMs after ex vivo Spn
978 infection (means ± SEM, n=12, data pooled from four independent experiments).
979 Significance was determined by log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test, unpaired 2-tailed t-test, 1-
980 way and 2-way ANOVA with Tukey's posthoc test; *p<0.05, **p<0.01. **(K)** Proposed
981 hypothesis: Severe IAV-induced pneumonia is characterized by massive leukocyte
982 recruitment, including neutrophils. Once in the alveoli, neutrophils start releasing
983 TNFSF14, which is sensed by TR-AMs through ligation to surfaced-expressed
984 receptors TNFRSF14 and LTbR, culminating in TR-AM death, which increases host
985 susceptibility to post-influenza pneumococcal pneumonia. AEC: alveolar epithelial
986 cells.

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Supplemental Figure 1. Gating strategy for the identification of different immune cell populations in murine BALF (A) and lung tissue (B) per flow cytometry analysis. Representative plots following multicolor staining of BALF and lung-tissue immune cells, as described in the 'Supplemental Methods' document. Gating

993 strategies were set according to the appropriate isotype and fluorescence minus one
994 (FMO) controls.
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Supplemental Figure 2. Immune cell kinetics in the lung tissue of IAV-infected mice over the infection course. Following BALF extraction, lungs of wild-type mice infected with 500ffu IAV were harvested at different time points. Immune cell populations were identified per flow cytometry analysis, including sessile TR-AMs (n=6-11) (A), neutrophils (n=5-10) (B), BMDM (n=5-10) (C), T cells (n=4-10) (D), B

1002 cells (n=3-7) (**E**), CD11b⁻ resident DCs, (n=6-7) (**F**), eosinophils (n=6-7) (**G**), NK cells
1003 (n=5-10) (**H**), CD11b⁺ DCs (n=6-7) (**I**), pDCs (n=6-7) (**J**), IM (n=6-7) (**K**), NK1.1⁺ NKT
1004 cells (n=5-10) (**L**), and Ly6C⁻ resident monocytes (n=6-7) (**M**). Data shown pooled from
1005 nine independent experiments, mean ± SEM is depicted. Significance was determined
1006 by 1-way ANOVA with Tukey's posthoc test; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p <0.001,
1007 ****p <0.0001. (p)DCs: (plasmacytoid) dendritic cells, IM: interstitial macrophages, NK:
1008 natural killer.

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 1012 **Supplemental Figure 3. TR-AM apoptosis can be attenuated through the use of**
 1013 **a caspase inhibitor. (A)** Gating strategy for the quantification of apoptotic TR-AMs in
 1014 the BALF of IAV-infected mice on days 0, 3, and 7 pi. **(B-C)** TR-AM viability following
 1015 treatment with 0.5µM staurosporine and different doses of a caspase-3 **(B)** or a
 1016 caspase-8 **(C)** inhibitor, values depicted as % survival of control. DMSO-treated cells
 1017 set at 100%. Graphs represent means ± SEM, n=4 per condition. Data pooled from
 1018 three independent experiments. Significance was determined by 2-way ANOVA with
 1019 Tukey's posthoc test; *p<0.05.

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Supplemental Figure 4. TNFSF14 orchestrates post-influenza TR-AM apoptosis in a cell-specific manner. (A-B) TNFSF14 receptor- positive cells as percentage of all BALF TR-AMs on day 3 pi **(A)** and percentage of apoptotic TR-AMs based on TNFSF14 receptor expression at the same time point **(B)**. Graphs represent means \pm

1026 SEM, n=8 per group, data pooled from two independent experiments. **(C)** Percentage
1027 of live transwell-seeded AEC after 24h IAV infection and treatment with rTNFSF14.
1028 Graphs represent means \pm SEM, n=9 per group, data pooled from two independent
1029 experiments. **(D-G)** Immunofluorescence analysis revealing a basolateral LTbR
1030 expression **(D,F)** and a non-preferential, cytoplasmic TNFRSF14 expression **(E,G)** on
1031 epithelial cells on days 0 **(D-E)** and 7 pi **(F-G)**. Scale bar for smaller panels set at 5 μ m,
1032 for larger panels set at 10 μ m **(D-E)** or 20 μ m **(F-G)**. Data representative of three
1033 independent experiments. **(H-I)** SDS-PAGE **(H)** and blue native PAGE **(I)** for TNFSF14
1034 in naïve and day 3 BALF samples with mouse rTNFSF14 (rmTNFSF14) as a positive
1035 control, demonstrating a single band at 26kDa upon denaturation. Under naïve
1036 conditions TNFSF14 appeared around 80kDa, reflecting the presence of the
1037 homotrimer in the BALF. Data representative of three independent experiments.
1038 Graphs represent means \pm SEM, n=6-8. Data pooled from three independent
1039 experiments. Significance was determined by unpaired 2-tailed t-test and two-way
1040 ANOVA; ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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Supplemental Figure 5. Lack of TNFSF14 attenuates TR-AM death without heavily affecting other cell population kinetics. (A-E) BALF neutrophils (A), BMDM (B), NK cells (C), NK1.1⁺ NKT cells (D), and T cells (E) on day 3 pi after rTNFSF14 treatment on days 1 and 2, n=9-11, means ± SEM, data pooled from three independent experiments. (F) Quantification of TR-AM numbers in the BALF of IAV-infected *Tnfsf10*^{-/-} mice on day 7 pi (means ± SEM, n=5-6, data pooled from three independent experiments). (G-J) Heat maps depicting fold change of necrosis- (G-H) and

1051 autophagy-related (**I-J**) genes on day 3 pi (**G, I**) and day 7 pi (**H, J**) over mock-infected
1052 wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} TR-AMs, n=3-5, data from five independent experiments. Wt data
1053 extracted from the data set presented in Figure 2E. (**K**) Viral titers in the BALF of wt
1054 and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice on day 3 pi (means ± SEM, n=4, data representative of three
1055 independent experiments). (**L-N**) Lung epithelial (EpCAM⁺, **L**), endothelial (CD31⁺, **M**),
1056 and mesenchymal cells (MC, **N**) of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice after IAV infection (means ±
1057 SEM, n=4-10, data pooled from ten independent experiments). (**O-S**) Immune cell
1058 populations in the BALF of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice, including neutrophils (**O**), BMDM (**P**),
1059 NK cells (**Q**), NK1.1⁺ NKT cells (**R**), and T cells (**S**). Graphs represent means ± SEM,
1060 n=5-13, data pooled from fourteen independent experiments, wt controls including data
1061 presented in Figure 1I. Significance was determined by unpaired 2-tailed t-test and 2-
1062 way ANOVA with Tukey's posthoc test; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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Supplemental Figure 6. Neutrophil depletion attenuates weight loss without affecting leukocyte influx after IAV infection. (A) Caspase-3/7 activation after treatment of day 3 TR-AMs with iBALF or co-culture with neutrophils plus a metalloproteinase inhibitor, n=6-9, data pooled from three independent experiments. **(B-E)** Neutrophils depicted as percentage of total leukocyte numbers after neutrophil

1070 depletion, in the blood (**B**), spleen (**C**), BALF (**D**), and lungs (**E**) of IAV-infected mice
1071 on day 7 pi (means \pm SEM, n=5-8, data pooled from two independent experiments).
1072 (**F**) Body weight as percentage of initial weight after IAV infection and neutrophil
1073 depletion, n=7-11, data pooled from four independent experiments. (**G-K**) BALF
1074 immune populations on day 7 pi after neutrophil depletion, including BMDM, (**G**), NK
1075 cells (**H**), NK1.1⁺NKT cells (**I**), T cells (**J**), and B cells (**K**). Graphs represent means \pm
1076 SEM, n=5-8, data from two independent experiments. Significance was determined by
1077 unpaired 2-tailed t-test for two groups, including the AUC between the two treatment
1078 groups for (**F**); *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p <0.001, ****p <0.0001.

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Supplemental Figure 7. Loss of TNFSF14 does not impact neutrophil influx, spleen bacterial burden, or TR-AM phagocytosis capacity after IAV/Spn co-infection. (A) Spn burden in the spleens of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice 9 days after IAV infection and 48h after Spn infection (means ± SEM, n=10, data pooled from eight different experiments). (B) Neutrophils depicted as percentage of total live cells in the BALF of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} mice at the same time point (means ± SEM, n=7-8, data pooled from five independent experiments). (C-D) Phagocytosis capacity of wt and *Tnfsf14*^{-/-} day 7 TR-AMs depicted as FITC signal normalized to non-infected TR-AMs (C) and percentage of FITC+ TR-AMs (phagocytic cells, D), following ex vivo incubation with pHrodo™ Green *Escherichia coli* BioParticles™ (means ± SEM, n=3-4, data representative of three independent experiments). Significance was determined by unpaired 2-tailed t-test.